

THE IMPACT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE: A FIELD RESEARCH IN INDUSTRIAL COMPANIES IN HODEIDA GOVERNORATE

Abdu Alamri ¹ and Abdulbaqi Thabet ²

¹ Associate Professor, Business Administration, University of Science and Technology.
Email: a.ameri@ust.edu.ye

² PhD Scholar, Business Administration Center, Sana'a University. Email: t.Thabit.cba@su.edu.ye

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Abstract

The current study aimed at determining the impact of emotional intelligence on the organizational performance of industrial companies in Hodeida governorate. The analytical descriptive method was followed using a questionnaire to collect the primary data, including the sample size of 212 individuals. The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and structural equation modeling using partial least squares (Smart-PLS-SEM). Based on the analysis, it was found that emotional intelligence has a positive impact on the organizational performance of the companies in consideration. In particular, positive impact is found for the self-awareness, sympathize, and social skill dimensions on organizational performance. In contrast, there was no recorded effect of the emotion management dimension on the organizational performance of the companies in consideration. In light of the results, it is recommended for the management of industrial companies to repeat programs and training courses on the behaviors of emotional intelligence and focus on establishing it as one of the elements of organizational culture in companies and to adopt emotional intelligence behaviors, among them standardization and requirements for selection, education, and promotion of employees in industrial companies.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Organizational Performance, Industrial Companies.

INTRODUCTION

Business organizations face many challenges in light of technological developments and political, social, and economic changes, the effects of which are reflected in the performance of companies and their employees. This requires that individuals possess advanced intellectual and skill capabilities in addition to social and emotional capabilities that are integrated with the intellectual and skill capabilities to address those effects in the performance of organizations. Emotional intelligence has become an important skill that people need in order to work collaboratively, increase their communication skills, and increase their professional skills and abilities. (Suchitra & Sasmita, 2021, p. 27) Emotional intelligence plays a crucial role in building effective emotions, which have a role in improving job and organizational performance (Faisal et al., 2022, p. 1429). Emotional intelligence is an important skill used in planning and managing organizational resources, selecting jobs, and increasing the ability to perceive and express feelings in order to understand and organize the organization's activities to improve organizational performance. (Tafamel & Ejechi, 2022, p. 771); the effectiveness of performance in organizations is affected by the ability of the organization's members to manage emotions within the work team (Noureen et al., 2020, p. 1247); emotional competence and emotional intelligence are the keys to the success of business performance in organizations, as those who possess emotional intelligence are able to assess situations, predict results, and realize the positive and negative aspects that can result from each situation. Position" (Nilam, 2022 P.8), and "those who possess a high level of emotional intelligence are able to

achieve high levels of success for their organizations because of their ability to understand others and to develop and develop the emotional and social capabilities and skills of those who work” (Alaa et al. 2020 P. 3).

Achieving strategic goals such as growth, expansion, survival, and continuity requires organizational performance that achieves improvement in the activities and operations that take place in the organization, development and advancement of its individuals, and an increase in the organization’s financial return (Al-Qarouda, 2020, P. 121). The successes achieved by organizations are based on focusing on effective organizational performance and measuring this performance; without focusing on organizational performance and measuring it, one cannot understand or know anything in the organization, nor can any success be achieved in it” (Al-Dabai, 2021, P. 2)

Industrial companies represent one of the most important pillars of the economy and the most important sectors that contribute to the development of society, increase its resources, and cover a large part of the needs of the local market. All of this requires improving the level of performance in them and developing them by focusing on human resources, which represent the most important elements of production in organizations, and attracting individuals who possess a high level of emotional intelligence in order to succeed and achieve their goals efficiently and effectively.

Despite the importance of emotional intelligence for organizations in their public and private sectors, its concept is not at the level required by administrators and workers in business organizations in the Arab environment in general and in the Yemeni environment in particular. This is due to the scarcity of research that has addressed the subject of emotional intelligence, especially its relationship with organizational performance. This study worked to determine the impact of emotional intelligence on the organizational performance of industrial companies in the Yemeni environment and to attract the focus of industrial companies towards enhancing the practice of emotional intelligence behaviors, which contributes to improving the level of their performance and makes them able to compete and face the challenges imposed by the conditions in the Yemeni environment.

LITERRATURE REVIEW

Emotional Intelligence

The real beginnings appeared in a series of scientific studies carried out by Mayer and Salovey when they used the term emotional intelligence in 1990 by identifying the elements of emotional intelligence and developing a scientific method to measure individual differences in emotional abilities. The results of their study showed the existence of differences in the abilities of individuals to identify their own emotions and the emotions of others and solve problems. (Alsamadoni, 2007 P.42), Emotional intelligence plays an important role in the success of the organization because it contributes to the formation of an appropriate and vibrant organizational environment that achieves harmony among its members. (Khokhar and Selvamurthi, 2016 P.22), and in the modern era, emotional intelligence has become an important skill for individuals and organizations that they need as much as they need professional abilities and skills, if not more important. (Pangerhami & Mohanty 2021 P. 26–27). Emotional intelligence means “the ability of individuals in organizations to understand and recognize their own feelings and the feelings of others, and the ability to make

decisions and solve problems inside and outside the organization by forming positive relationships with others.” (Mohana & Zuhural, 2022, p. 14), Supriadi & Sefnedi (2017, p. 101) defined it as “the ability to understand, control, and recognize emotions, meanings, and problem solving based on them, which involves understanding emotion feelings, cognitive ability, and emotions. Understand and manage emotional information”. The researchers defined emotional intelligence as the ability of individuals working in industrial companies to understand, regulate, and control their own emotions, observe and understand the emotions of others, empathize with them, and form positive relationships with them to ensure improving the level of performance in industrial companies and achieving their goals efficiently and effectively. There are two main models of emotional intelligence: mental ability models and mixed models (Bin-Gharial, 2015 P. 76). Models of mental abilities mean the individual’s ability to manage and organize his emotions and think about them, and the most important pioneers of this trend are Mayer & Salovey, who identified the dimensions of emotional intelligence in managing emotions, using emotions, understanding emotions, and managing emotions. (Moussalli, 2013 P. 28). Mixed models: this means combining personal qualities and emotions in their social context through social activity and interaction with others. The most important pioneer of this trend is Goleman, who defined the dimensions of emotional intelligence as self-awareness, emotional management, self-motivation, empathy, and social skills (Goolman, 2001 P. 85). For the four cognitive dimensions he identified, Mayer and Salovey (1997) are the most commonly used dimensions to measure the level of emotional intelligence of individuals in organizations (Alaa et al. 2020 P. 4). This study identified the dimensions of emotional intelligence in four dimensions: the first is self-awareness, which means the individual’s ability to understand his feelings and control his responses and reactions (Makker & Basu, 2019 P. 462), and the second is emotion management, which is defined as an individual’s ability to deal with negative problems that may have a negative impact on his professional life, his public life, and his level of performance (Asrar alhaq et al., 2017 p. 88). Third, empathy indicates the ability of individuals to be aware of the needs of others, sense their feelings and fears, understand their point of view and accept them, and enhance their capabilities and expectations (Mohana & Zuhural, 2022, p. 15). Fourth, social skills mean the individual's ability to understand and respond correctly to the societal situation while forming a positive relationship that achieves the organization's goals (Kassem & Ahmed, 2021, p. 154).

Organizational Performance

Organizational performance is one of the most important topics that managers care about in both industrial and service organizations. By measuring organizational performance, the level of the organization’s achievement of its goals becomes clear, whether its short-term or long-term goals, and on the basis of it, managers can take what they deem appropriate to achieve the goals that were planned efficiently and effectively , and organizational performance represents a comprehensive system includes measures of good management performance, and indicators of the existence of control methods that prevent any party related to the facility internally and externally from negatively influencing the facility’s activities, while ensuring the optimal use of available resources and achieving its goals efficiently (Al-Mu’baqi, 2020 p. 85), and helps industrial companies to control And controlling its work, as it helps in identifying the performance of employees and their training needs, and also helps in the process of organizational development, and facilitates the communication process between

employees and management” (Aksamari ,2020, p.79), and gives leaders a clear picture and complete and accurate information about the performance in the organization, including It helps it to conduct a comprehensive evaluation review of the operations in the organization and determine the extent of the ability of the administrative units in the organization to achieve its goals (Puja & Shikha, 2016, p. 69).

The concept of organizational performance is one of the broad and developed concepts whose components are characterized by dynamism. This is due to the different nature of the work of organizations, their circumstances, and the continuous change in their internal and external work environments, which has led to a multiplicity of definitional content for the concept of organizational performance (Muslim, 2017: 49). It is defined as achieving the goals and objectives set by planning. Strategic and profound, it is affected by improved employee performance. It is measured in terms of the financial perspective, the customer perspective, the internal business perspective, and learning (Jose, 2019, p. 15), and it is defined (Tafamel & Ejechi, 2022, 771) as a means of monitoring, controlling, and evaluating the organization’s performance resulting from the interaction between its productive elements and ensuring the achievement of the objectives of the organization efficiently and effectively. Accordingly, organizational performance in industrial companies can be defined as the result of the interaction of the components of industrial companies with each other and their response to internal and external influences to achieve optimal exploitation of their resources and produce goods that satisfy customers’ desires, achieve their satisfaction, and achieve the company’s goals efficiently and effectively.

The current study adopted the elements of the balanced scorecard model in terms of dimensions to measure organizational performance, as it provides a balanced view of the factors important for the success of organizations. “The balanced scorecard model is characterized by the fact that it contributes to achieving social responsibility, community service, environmental protection, and increasing employee skills and work effectiveness in organizations” (Al-Mahrouq,2017 p.34). “The balanced scorecard model gives a clear vision of the current and future status of the organization and measures the progress of the organization’s performance level in the direction that achieves its strategic objectives and links short-term operational control to the vision and strategy of the organization” (Ranjit and Aron 2010, p. 249–251). "It examines observable characteristics of the balanced scorecard model (i.e., measures common to multiple units vs. measures unique to particular units) that may limit managers' ability to fully exploit the information found in a diverse set of performance measures (Marlyse and Stavin, 2000, p. 285).

Each business unit in the organization develops its own balanced scorecard model to reflect its goals and strategy. While some of these measures are likely to be common across all subsidiaries or units, others will be unique to each business unit. The Balanced Scorecard is “an administrative system that aims to help the organization translate its vision, mission, values, strategic objectives, and strategies into a set of standards, measures, and dimensions to give the parties of the organization in general and senior management managers in particular a clear and comprehensive picture of the performance of their organizations” (Abu Madi, 2018 p. 39). The balanced scorecard model includes several aspects, firstly the financial dimension, which expresses the extent of the organization’s ability to use its available financial resources efficiently and effectively in a way that benefits the organization (Al-Qarouda, 2020,

72), and it includes many basic criteria such as achieving high profit and balanced growth in profitable revenues from activities. Investment, reducing costs to the maximum possible extent to achieve the highest possible effectiveness, and maximizing shareholders' wealth by increasing the return on investment (Chavan, 2009), Secondly, after customers, this dimension shows the extent of the organization's ability to fulfill the requirements and needs of customers for goods and services, and The standards used in this dimension include after-sales services, low cost, responding to customers' desires, and thirdly, the internal operations dimension. This dimension focuses on controlling and monitoring all vital internal activities and events that distinguish the organization from other organizations and the means through which they are achieved (Abu Madi, 2018, 35). Meeting the needs and expectations of customers is concerned with performing internal manufacturing operations and activities and controlling important links in the manufacturing, administrative, and other chains in an effort to address deviations, develop performance, and align operations with the general directions of the organization (Farrag, 2020, p. 37); Fourth is the learning and growth dimension. This dimension measures the organization's ability to innovate, which ensures its survival and continuity in the long term by directing individuals towards continuous development and improvement. (Farrag, 2020, p. 36)

Emotional Intelligence and Organizational Performance

Emotional intelligence is considered an important concept in the administrative field as it is an influential factor in various administrative topics such as organizational performance, job performance, negotiation, conflict management, and leadership. (Zehier et al., 2019, p. 266) , In order to analyze the relationship between EI and the level of organizational performance in more detail, different competencies of EI and different types of organizational performance, such as financial, employee, and operational performance, have been linked (Maja, 2022, p. 6). The efficiency and effectiveness of organizations are affected by many variables, and among these variables is emotional intelligence, which is an important variable that contributes to improving the performance of organizations. Organizations that want to achieve success must not be satisfied with only technical and intellectual knowledge but rather need to clarify the behaviors of employees' emotional intelligence and train them in it because of its benefits. Of a major role in achieving the success, development, and sustainable development of the organization in the long term (Al-Mutairi and Al-Khashali, 2021: 156), A study by Bell Zeheir et.al. 2019)reported that there was a relationship between emotional intelligence and the efficiency and effectiveness of performance in organizations, as emotional intelligence helps in providing a better job environment for workers, which in turn contributes to performance." employees to fully perform their jobs and achieve better performance for the organization" (Mhagma, 2019, 182). Emotional intelligence improves the performance of organizations, and it is necessary to train leaders and individuals working in the organization to practice emotional intelligence behaviors. Increasing their ability to practice these behaviors positively affects the financial dimension. And customers and operations, and contributes to the development and growth of the organization (Al-Dabai, 2021: 135). Emotional intelligence is linked to the performance of various organizations, as performance in them depends on the ability of individuals to interact successfully with others and on their ability to confront adverse behaviors, control their emotions, control their feelings, and motivate others and create positive relationships with them (Melhem

et al., 2020: 280). There have been many studies that dealt with emotional intelligence and organizational performance and clarified the relationship or impact between them, such as the study by Tafamel and Ejechi (2022), which aimed to determine the effect of emotional intelligence on organizational performance at the University of Benin in Nigeria. The study indicated the presence of a positive effect, but without statistical significance, of emotional intelligence on organizational performance. In the university sector, and the study (Eid, 2022), which showed the presence of a statistically significant effect of emotional intelligence on the organizational performance of Egyptian pharmaceutical companies. The study also indicated the presence of an effect of the dimensions of self-awareness and social skills on the organizational performance of the companies under study. The study recommended the need to focus on enhancing the behavior of emotional intelligence for its important role in improving the level of organizational performance in pharmaceutical companies, and the study (Al-Dubai, 2021) showed that there is a positive effect of emotional intelligence and servant leadership on organizational performance in Yemeni commercial banks. With its dimensions (self-awareness, managing emotions, managing the emotions of others, social relationships, and empathy) in organizational performance in Yemeni commercial banks, the study recommended the necessity of raising the level of emotional intelligence among workers in commercial banks by making emotional intelligence one of the basic behaviors in accepting and promoting employees therein. Helena and Beatrex (2021) also conducted a study that aimed to determine the impact of emotional intelligence on organizational performance in some Hungarian companies. The most important results were the positive impact of emotional intelligence on organizational performance in the companies studied. There is a positive effect of the dimensions (self-awareness and self-management) on organizational performance in the companies studied, and there is no effect of the dimension of managing the emotions of others on organizational performance in the companies studied. The study recommended the need to focus on developing emotional intelligence behaviors and creating training programs to raise the level of the ability of employees in companies to practice emotional intelligence behaviors at a level that ensures improved organizational performance. A study (Suschitra and Sasmita, 2021) showed a positive impact of emotional intelligence on organizational performance in private and public hospitals in the Indian city of Odessa. It recommended continuing to improve the level of the practice of emotional intelligence by hospital workers to raise the level of performance in it and reduce the occurrence of problems in health facilities, and a study (Suganthi & Singaravelloo, 2020) indicated that there is a significant positive relationship between emotional intelligence and organizational performance, as it improves the efficiency and effectiveness of performance in Malaysian public administrations, and emotionally intelligent employees also contribute to creating a more effective work environment by staying in a positive mood under negative and difficult circumstances, this allows them to deal with difficult situations in a calm manner, provide the most appropriate solution, and lead the rest employees towards successfully achieving the organization's goals.

Cognitive Model

The cognitive model represents an illustration of the independent variable (emotional intelligence) and the dependent variable (organizational performance). The dimensions of emotional intelligence in this research include self-awareness, emotional management, social skills, and empathy. The dimensions include financial,

customer, internal operations, and learning and growth. The cognitive model shows that this research is based on testing the impact of emotional intelligence in its dimensions on organizational performance in industrial companies in Hodeida Governorate, and the following figure shows that:

Figure 1: Cognitive Model

Research Hypothesis

The Main Hypothesis

There is a statistically significant impact of emotional intelligence on organizational performance in industrial companies in Hodeida Governorate.

B: Sub-Hypotheses

1. There is a statistically significant impact of self-awareness on organizational performance in industrial companies in Hodeida Governorate.
2. There is a statistically significant impact of emotional management on organizational performance in industrial companies in Hodeida Governorate.
3. There is a statistically significant impact of social skills on organizational performance in industrial companies in Hodeida Governorate.
4. There is a statistically significant impact of empathy on organizational performance in industrial companies in Hodeida Governorate.

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive analytical approach was used to describe and determine the level of the study variables as it is in the reality of the industrial companies investigated by collecting data from the study sample using a questionnaire that was developed to achieve the objectives of this study and testing its hypotheses using appropriate statistical methods, through which the impact of emotional intelligence on organizational performance was measured. The study population represented the industrial sector in Hodeida Governorate. The seven largest industrial companies were selected from among the industrial companies registered with the Office of Trade and Industry in Hodeida Governorate. The study relied on selecting industrial companies

that had been established for more than 10 years, and the size of their employees was more than 200. The size of the population was 471 individuals, including administrators working in administrative units. The sample size was determined based on the model (Morgan & Krejci 1970), which determined the size of the study sample at 212 individuals. Questionnaires were distributed to them, and the questionnaires retrieved, which amounted to 194, were eligible for analysis. The study sample was distributed according to the variables of gender, age, years of experience, educational level, and job, as shown in Table 1:

Gender	Count	Percent
Male	176	90.7%
Female	18	9.3%
Total	194	100%
Age	Count	Percent
Less 30y	32	16.5%
30-40 Y	88	45.3%
41-50Y	48	24,6
> 55Y	26	13,6
Total	194	100%
Years of experieence	Count	Percent
Less 5 y	40	20.6%
6-10Y	50	25.8%
11-15Y	53	27.3%
> 15Y	51	26.3%
Total	194	100%
EDUCATION LEVEL	Count	Percent
High School	8	4.1%
Diploma	35	18.1%
Bachelor's Degree	144	74.2%
MASTER AND PDH	7	3.6%
Total	194	100%
Administrative Level	Count	Percent
Senior	7	3.6%
Middle	90	46.4%
Minimum	97	50%
Total	194	100

RESULT

Result of Descriptive Statistics of Application of Emotional Intelligence

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics Of Implementing Emotional Intelligence Dimension

Emotional Intelligence Dimension	Mean	Standard DIVIATION	%	Answer level	Order
Self-awareness	5.0979	0.86981	72.8%	Fairly high	2
Emotional management	4.9237	0.93872	70.3%	Fairly high	3
Social skills	5.3474	1.01262	76.4%	High	1
Empathy	4.7134	1.08629	67.3%	Fairly high	4
Emotional Intelligence (Total)	5.0206	0.83301	71.7%	Fairly high	

The previous table shows that the participants' practice of emotional intelligence was at a fairly high level, with an average of (5.0206) and a percentage of (71.7%). The level of practicing social skills was in first place with an average of (5.3474) with a percentage of (76.4%), while the level of practicing the empathy dimension was in last place with an average of (4.7134) with a percentage of (67.3%). These results give an indication that the focus of senior management in the surveyed companies on enhancing individuals' practice of emotional intelligence behaviors was not at the required level. The researcher attributes the reason to the fact that the concept of emotional intelligence is considered one of the modern concepts in the field of business organization management, as most departments in industrial companies have no Plans are made to develop these behaviors through awareness and training courses and disseminate them as an organizational culture. After social skills, it came in first place. This is due to the strong social bond between colleagues because they work with each other for long periods and the culture and customs of Yemeni society, which place a high degree of emphasis on forming relationships. Social within and outside the organization. The researchers also attribute the fact that the empathy dimension ranked lowest to the fact that the behavior of empathy depends to a high degree on the human sense of individuals and their ability to understand the feelings of others and the needs of working to meet them.

Result of Descriptive Statistics for the Application of Organizational Performance

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Implementing Organizational Performance Dimensions

Organizational performance Dimension	Mean	Standard DIVIATION	%	Answer level	Order
Financial	5.5897	0.86155	79.9%	High	1
Costumers	5.2804	1.07931	75.4%	High	3
Internal operation	5.2801	1.01811	74.7%	High	4
Learning and growth	5.4814	1.0308	78.3%	High	2
Organizational performanc (Total)	5.3956	0.83369	77.1%	High	

It is clear from the previous numbers that the level of availability of organizational performance in industrial companies, according to the responses of the sample members, was high with an average of (5.3956) and relative importance of (77.1%), and the financial dimension came in the highest rank with a high level with an average of (5.5897) and relative importance of (79.9%), while the learning and growth dimension ranked lowest in terms of the sample's degree of approval with an average of (5.2801) and relative importance of (74.7%). These results explain the extent of high interest in organizational performance by industrial companies, as the level of availability of all dimensions was high and reflected the financial dimension's obtaining the rank The first is due to the commercial nature of industrial companies, as they mainly aim to achieve profit by focusing on aspects that increase revenues, such as product diversification, increasing market share, and reducing costs to increase the financial return rate. The learning and growth dimension of obtaining the lowest rank is also due to the interest of company management. The industrial sector, using advanced technological techniques in training, updating training programs to keep pace with changes and developments, and encouraging individuals to participate in creative ideas that contribute to improving and developing companies, was not at the required level.

D: Testing the Main Sub-Hypotheses

First: Testing the Main Hypothesis

The main hypothesis is that "there is a statistically significant impact of emotional intelligence on organizational performance in industrial companies in Hodeida governorate."

Table 4: Impact Model Estimation between Emotional Intelligence and Organizational Performance

Dependant variable	Path	Independent variable	(R ²)	Beta	Standard deviation	T	P-Value
Emotional intelligence	-->	organizational performance	0.502	0.774	0.031	3.478	0.000

The previous table shows that the coefficient of determination (R²) for the main hypothesis is (0.502), which is an average value and indicates that emotional intelligence explains (50.2%) of the variance or changes in organizational performance in industrial companies, and that (49.8%) of the variance is explained by variables.

The beta value was 0.774, which indicates that there is a strong positive relationship between emotional intelligence and organizational performance in industrial companies and that there is a statistically significant effect of emotional intelligence on organizational performance, as increasing emotional intelligence by one degree It contributes to increasing organizational performance in industrial companies by (77.4%), which is confirmed by the T value (24.66), which is statistically significant, as its value was greater than (2), as well as the P-value equal to (0.00), which is statistically significant when the significance level is less than 0.05.

From the above results of testing the main hypothesis, it is clear that there is a statistically significant effect of emotional intelligence on organizational performance in industrial companies, and thus the main hypothesis is accepted. The result of this study is consistent with the result of a study (Magill et al. 2022), which showed the presence of an effect of managing emotional intelligence on organizational performance in Medium and large companies in Siberia, and the study (Al-Dubai, 21 20) which revealed that there is an impact of emotional intelligence on the organizational performance of Yemeni banks, and the study (Helena and Beatrix, 2021) which indicated the presence of an impact of emotional intelligence on the organizational performance in Hungarian companies, and the study (and Zuhair et al., 2019) which showed the presence of a statistically significant effect of emotional intelligence on organizational performance in universities, and the study (Sousan, et al. 2015) which showed the presence of an effect of emotional intelligence on organizational performance in Malaysian industrial companies.

Second: Sub-Hypothesis Testing

Table 5: Impact Model Estimation Between Talent Attraction And Emotional Intelligence

Dependent variable	Path	Independent variable	Beta	Standard deviation	T	P-Value
Self-awareness	---->	organizational performance	0.2410	0.069	3.478	0.001
Emotional management	---->	organizational performance	0.051	0.088	0.578	0.546
Social skills	---->	organizational performance	0.383	0.079	4.835	0.000
Empathy	---->	organizational performance	0.213	0.079	2.701	0.007

There is a statistically significant effect of self-awareness on organizational performance, where the beta value was 0.241, the t-value was 3.478, and the P-value was 0.001a, which is statistically significant at a significance level less than 0.05 and can be It is said that self-awareness contributes to increasing organizational performance by 24.1%, and therefore we accept the first sub-hypothesis, which states: "There is a statistically significant effect of self-awareness on organizational performance in industrial companies in Hodeidah Governorate."

- There is no statistically significant effect of emotional management on organizational performance, as the beta value was 0.051, the t-value was 0.578, and the P-value was 0.564, which is not statistically significant at a significance level less than 0.05. Therefore, we reject the second sub-hypothesis, which states: "There is a statistically significant effect of emotional management on organizational performance in industrial companies in Hodeidah Governorate."
- There is a statistically significant effect of social skills on organizational performance, where the beta value was 0.383, the t-value was 4.835, and the P-value was 0.000, which is statistically significant at a significance level less than 0.01, and it can be said that social skills contribute to increasing organizational performance by 38.3%. Therefore, we accept the third sub-hypothesis, which states: "There is a statistically significant effect of social skills on organizational performance in industrial companies in Hodeidah Governorate."
- There is a statistically significant effect of empathy on organizational performance, where the beta value was 0.213, the t-value was 2.701, and the P-value was 0.007, which is statistically significant at a significance level less than 0.01. It can be said that empathy contributes to increasing organizational performance by 21.3%. Therefore, we accept the fourth sub-hypothesis, which states: "There is a statistically significant effect of empathy on organizational performance in industrial companies in Hodeidah Governorate."

The results of the current study in the presence of an effect of self-awareness and social skills on organizational performance agreed with the study (Tafamel & Ejechi, 2022) (Eid, 2022) (Al-Dabai, 2021) (Helena & Beatrix, 2021) (Gichuhi et al., 2019). It is consistent with the study (Al-Dubai, 2021) in the presence of an impact of empathy on organizational performance, and it is also consistent with the results of the study by Tafamel& Ejechi (2022) (Eid, 2022) (Gichuhi et al., 2019) in the absence of an impact of emotional management on organizational performance.

CONCLUSION

According to the results of the reviewed research and the data analysis stated previously, several conclusions were drawn:

- Individuals working in industrial companies practice emotional intelligence behaviors at a fairly high level.
- The most widely practiced dimension of emotional intelligence in industrial companies was the social skills dimension, which was at a high level; the least was emotional management.
- The least commonly practiced indicators of emotional intelligence behavior in industrial companies are putting the interests of others before personal interests and the ability to separate decision-making from personal reactions.
- Industrial companies are highly interested in achieving organizational performance from the perspective of the balanced scorecard.
- Industrial companies show greater interest in the financial dimension than other dimensions of organizational performance.
- Industrial companies are keen to improve their financial performance by reducing costs and increasing their market share to achieve high revenues and provide liquidity on an ongoing basis.
- There is a positive impact of emotional intelligence on organizational performance in industrial companies.
- The most influential dimensions of emotional intelligence on the organizational performance of industrial companies are the social skills dimension, then self-awareness, and the least influential dimension is the dimension of empathy.
- There is no effect of the emotion management dimension on the organizational performance of the industrial companies under study.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- The need for the management of industrial companies to focus on maintaining a high level of organizational performance and working to enhance it by adopting the balanced scorecard as an integrated system supported by senior management while paying attention to all its components in a balanced manner
- Industrial companies prepare training programs and courses on emotional intelligence behaviors and focus on consolidating them as one of the elements of organizational culture.
- Adopting emotional intelligence behaviors is among the selection and appointment criteria for employees in industrial companies.
- Adopting the availability of emotional intelligence behaviors is among the requirements that must be met for promotions in industrial companies.
- Implementing applied training programs for workers in industrial companies on self-management and emotion management to increase individuals' ability to understand themselves, manage their emotions, and act positively with others

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